

Sexuality in third old age in “The Temptation to Be Happy” of Lorenzo Marone

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ABSTRACT

Sexuality in third old age is a topic that has been explored more often in films and contemporary literature of the XXI Century than before.

Life span has increased and it seems that there is a need to imagine who it is going to be like sexuality after sixty years old.

In *The Temptation to Be Happy*, the principal, Cesar Annunziata, is a seventy-seven years old man who is a widower but has not quit to enjoy his sexuality.

The novel describes his private life, with a prostitute who later becomes his couple and with whom he has intimate moments such as holding hands that is scarier than being in bed together or seeing each other naked.

Cesar has two children and a grandchild. Cesar discovers that his daughter has an affair and that his son is gay. This is important to analyze because the principal believes that he is liberal and open-minded but it is not easy for him to accept his children's secrets, incoherencies and preferences

Sexuality in third old age people will be analyzed according to the following categories: aging body, sexual desire in old people, the obsession of being forever young, and aging in narrative.

Key words: literature, old people, sexuality

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays it is quite common finding novels and films with main characters in their third old aged, but the way they are presented have changed in last decades.

Third old aged principal characters in contemporary literature and films are independent, they enjoy their sexuality, they have romantic relationships, they hang out with friends, they are in touch with family members but it is quite common that they have to fight for keeping their autonomy and control of their financial accounts.

This paper explores the sexuality in the novel *The Temptation to Be Happy* of Lorenzo Marone. The principal character, Cesar Annunziata, is a seventy-seven-year-old widower who enjoys having a relationship with a mature person with whom he first had sex but it changed to a romantic relationship.

This novel demonstrates that it is never too late to enjoy sexuality, and it is possible to desire and to be desired by others and it does not matter that the body it is not perfect.

2. SEXUALITY IN THIRD OLD AGE

For many people the subject of sexuality is a taboo subject and even more so if it is about thinking about the sexuality of the elderly. Fortunately, every day increases the number of researches that have been interested in knowing how to improve the quality of life in all aspects during old age, including sex life and it has been discovered that this is possible in old age and can even be very satisfactory.

With the increase in life expectancy in people, every day the number of older adults grows in society and therefore the latter needs to adapt to the needs of this growing population.

This phenomenon could not be foreign in the cinema or in literature, more and more commercial and independent films and novels that show old characters in different facets are seen.

Ana Belén Martín Cristóbal (2013) states that the need for physical contact and emotional intimacy is resolved with parents during childhood and with friends and partners during adulthood and old age, while the need for sexual intimacy is resolved with the couple during youth, adult life and old age.

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Therefore, it is important that the older adult can meet the needs of body contact, emotional intimacy and sexual intimacy.

Corporeity is part of the dimension of sexual experience, which implies self-adjustment, acceptance and gratitude to one's own body. This is part of the process of attraction, conquest and seduction implied in sexuality, without forgetting that the body is capable of giving and receiving pleasure (García Rodríguez, 2013, 79).

In relation to this issue, it is also worth remembering some myths related to the sexuality of the elderly that could be eradicated with an adequate sexual education: the activity of the elderly is abnormal, they lose their sexual desire irretrievably, they are unable to feel pleasure, they are not able to awaken sexual pleasure in the other and sexual activity is exhausted if there were sexual excesses during youth (Moreno, 2010, 94), decrepitude, loss of intellectual and physical abilities, deterioration of the body due to aging, ugliness or lack of capacity to provoke interest in another person, being unattractive (Vásquez-Bronfman, 2006, 282).

Clara Coria (2012) shows a cultural contradiction about the enjoyment of sexuality after sixty years and that is related to gender issues:

"It is not good for a sixty-year-old woman to be excited and sighing, while at the same time appreciating that a man in his sixties makes use of his sexuality (and abuse if possible) as an expression of undisputed vitality" (Coria, 2012: 32).

In *The Temptation to Be Happy*, the enjoyment of sexuality occurs equally in men and women in old age, it is narrated the enjoyment of Cesar and his lover Rossana, the two feel and take pleasure, but at the same time you can find a stereotype: women enjoy with the lover and not always with the husband.

Sexuality in *The Temptation to Be Happy*

Clara Coria explains the following:

"It should be noted that there are many women who enjoy their lovers what they never got to enjoy with their husbands, but very few feel confident enough and dare to tell their daughters that culture is responsible not only for hiding, but also for disproving" (Coria, 2012: 25).

Although there is a quote obtained from the novel that reveals this stereotype of the male in the third age who could walk with a woman much younger than him:

"I do not know if I'm pissed off by the dirty thought that has crossed his mind or feel proud because he still sees me capable of seducing a thirtysomething" (Marone, 2017: 102).

In *The Temptation to Be Happy*, Cesar recognizes the following:

"You can make a whore have a good time {...}. But I do not know how to act as a loving grandfather, I am not capable of giving love to the one who corresponds to it" (Marone, 2017: 134).

It is noted that it facilitates intercourse, giving physical pleasure, but not giving love, or being affectionate. There are other moments in the novel where the difficulty for the intimacy of the protagonist is appreciated:

"She turns around and laughs. Then he takes my hand and we intertwine our fingers. Well, incredible, a chill runs through my arm to reach my back. I think the last woman I had such an intimate relationship with was my wife. My wrinkled and stained hands have become more accustomed to touching some buttocks than touching other hands. It is the age that advances and devours the little poetry that still shines in my belly" (Marone, 2017: 120).

It is seen that with the wife maybe eroticism did not enjoy it so much, but she did have intimacy, while, with Rossana, she enjoyed her sexuality, but she had not had intimacy and the act of holding hands has a tremendous impact on him.

There are more moments in which he describes seemingly simple moments, but so intimate that they become highly significant

"I'm already home when I get a message on my cell phone. It's her. After countless attempts, I get to read the text. He says: Thank you for the splendid night. I will not forget it! My eyes get wet, so I throw the phone to the couch and go to the bathroom. Tell me if at my age I can still be moved by the phrase of a woman. Sitting on the toilet, my lips decide to break the silence of the house: -I just wanted to tell you that tonight a woman took me by the hand and has made me excited

as I did not for a long time. I know, it's not right that I come to tell you about it, but you're the only one I wanted to tell you about. Good evening" (Marone, 2017: 121).

The novel shows a situation that occurs more often in contemporary relationships: first to know each other in the sexual, then emotional:

"The problem is that we have made the road backwards: first we have gone to bed together and then we have stayed for dinner" (Marone, 2017: 109).

Zigmunt Bauman (2010), in his book *Liquid Love*, talks about relationships in our time and reflects on the fragility of love and the links between people, the lack of commitment in relationships, the relationships seen as investments and the end of how loneliness causes insecurity which can also be felt even in a couple due to lack of privacy.

As an example of this, the following quote is presented: I've been to Rossana for two years and the furthest place from the bed where we've exchanged two words has been the kitchen. I know their striae much better than their culinary tastes; could join their moles as if they were the points of the *Settisemana Enigmistica*². I do not even know if he has a sister "(Marone, 2017: 31).

In this meeting you can see how little she knows Rossana in two years, how everything has focused on physical pleasure, just knowing her body but not the person.

Likewise, César thinks that "it is much more intimate to share a kitchen than a bed" (Marone, 2017: 35).

Bauman (2010) also explains that, of all the impulses, inclinations and natural tendencies of the human being, sexual desire was and is the most social, since it is directed towards another human being. Union is what human beings want to escape from loneliness.

This is seen in *The Temptation to Be Happy*, the protagonist sought to feel accompanied through having relationships with a prostitute, but then begins to have another kind of relationship that is what makes you feel complete.

In the following quotes the protagonist recognizes how Rossana has improved his life:

"If it did not exist, I would be a worse person, more nervous, perhaps more lonely and, no doubt, more repressed" (Marone, 2017: 31).

"She makes me feel sociable. It is one of her strengths, one of her strengths, apart from her tits, obviously: Rosana makes you feel a better man "(Marone, 2017: 35).

There is not much antecedent of the sexual life of the personage of Rossana before it knew Caesar, but it is shown in the novel of the relation of César before to be widowed with his wife Caterina, with that did not pass it so well. Both had extramarital affairs, but Cesar did not know that his wife had been unfaithful and discovers him as a widower and that hurts him a lot, even though he was not faithful either.

Conclusions

The *Temptation to Be Happy* shows the active sexual life of a third old aged man, but it also gives an example of the possibility of having pleasure, being in love and to be happy at the last days of our lives.

And it is possible to find similar stories that talk about the sexuality and love lives of aging people.

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